

Application of Sensors and Fuzzy Logic in SMART FARMING

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Abstract—*One of the great challenges in the current scenario is to meet out the needs of food for growing population. Current conventional method of farming is not sufficient to satisfy the need. So adequate changes are required. It is achieved by using IoT and Wireless sensor network in farming . This Paper describes the utilization of smart technique in agriculture by exploiting sensors and wireless sensor network. Using sensors of soil moisture , temperature and NPK, quantitative analyses of the fore said parameters were achieved and based on the numerical values drip irrigation is performed for adequate supply of them consequently avoiding deficit and excess administration of water and nutrients. The sufficient quantity to be supplied is decided by computing the values obtained from the sensors with the application of Fuzzy logic techniques. As a result of which, both pollution by excess nutrition and less productivity by nutritional deficiency are avoided. The additional advantage of the discussed work is that the every intricate working of the system is communicated to the agriculturist by SMS through GSM. The same is considered as the alert given to the agriculturist to provide the plants with water and nutrients on time.*

Keywords: *IoT, Wireless Sensor Network, NPK Sensor, GSM, SMS, Fuzzy Logic*

1. INTRODUCTION

The research in IoT in agriculture area enhanced various aspects to improve the quality and quantity of productivity of agriculture. Researchers have been working on many different projects on soil attributes, different weather conditions as well as scouting crops. Food being the one of the fundamental needs of entire living systems, maintenance of its quantity and quality has become real challenge in the world of increasing population. And also extreme weather conditions and rising climate change, and environmental impact made by the sophistications of human beings are great challenges in the farming practices to sustain the quality of the farm product. The demand for more food has to be met, to feed the exploding population. Hence adequate modifications and application of new technologies are very much required in the field of agriculture to increase the productivity and to maintain the quality. This leads the need for introducing IoT in Farming methods. Application of technology from lab to land and analysis of physical entities of a cultivation land from land to lab are two oppositely directed highways that are to be established to develop a self sufficient society and a powerful nation. Therefore the establishment of proper connection between the two extreme ends namely computational scientists and agriculturists are needed. The urgent need of our nation is smart farming in order to produce food of high quality and quantitatively sufficient to meet the requirement of the increasing population and decreasing of the cultivation area. To meet the growing demand for vegetables due to population growth, the adoption of Smart Farming techniques powered by IoT technologies is encouraged. This approach enables farmers to minimize waste and boost productivity, optimizing everything from fertilizer usage to the number of trips made by farm machinery. These could be achieved by the application of modern ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) in agriculture.

1.1 The main characteristics of smart farming using IoT

- 1) Monitoring: Sensors placed on the farm supply information about their environment. These data can be the source for smart farming. A Data obtained from the farming with the sensors are much faster than the Traditional farming system.
- 2) Control: Using the data obtained from the monitoring phase, agricultural land can be controlled by the software embedded within them or that resides in the cloud. This Remote control mechanism of smart farming increases profit and can reduce the number of employees needed and avoids regular physical visitation.
- 3) Optimization: The Farm Yielding can be increased by using proper Data analytics and Algorithms .
- 4) Autonomy: The above three mentioned steps(Monitoring, Control and Optimization) allow the smart farming as an autonomous operation with self-coordination and self-diagnosis.

2. Literature Survey

The recent development in the application of IoT in agriculture helps to achieve improvement in various aspects pertaining to quality and quantity of the agricultural products. The literature in this field is much scattered and shows that the researchers are much interested in the analyses of soil parameters, weather impacts and scouting crops.

The advancement in the electronic things have much reduced the size, efficiency and accuracy of sensors. They find numerous applications in the agriculture to solve important problems.

2.1 Development of wireless sensors and IoT in agri-food sector

Internet of Things (IoT) is a collection of wireless sensors network used to enable application like optimization of irrigation in agriculture. The one of the main components of the IOT is Wireless sensor network. The sensors will be helpful in making proper irrigation to avoid the wastage of water. It is achieved by using the WSN technology. The system is capital-intensive and technologically advanced, designed to grow food in a clean and sustainable manner on a large scale. In the context of IoT-based smart farming, sensor applications are employed to precisely monitor key parameters such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and more. By gathering data from wireless sensor networks and comparing these values with the optimal conditions required for specific crops, efficient irrigation practices can be implemented, ensuring resource optimization.

Table1:Usage of Wireless Sensor in Smart Farming

Author Name& Year	Title	Work done	Disadvantage / point for improvement
Morais et al.(1996)[1]	Solar Data acquisition wireless network for agricultural applications	In wireless sensors	Used only for temperature / can be used for moisture and nutrients
Sudha et al.(2011)[2]	Energy efficient data transmission in automatic irrigation system using wireless sensor networks	In wireless sensors and networking	Soil moisture and temperature monitored/ can be improved for macro nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium.
Xiaohong et al.(2009) [3]	A water-saving irrigation system based on fuzzy control technology and wireless sensor network	In water irrigation	Fuzzy controlled water irrigation/ Not applied for drip irrigation
Zhang et al(2011)[4]	A calibration method of detecting soil water content based on the information-sharing in wireless sensor	In sensors	Sensor used to find water content in the soil /nutrition, temperature and other vital parameters are

	network		not monitored
Dubey et al.(2011) [5]	Wireless sensor network based remote irrigation control system and automation using DTMF code	In electronic signals	Water supply by spray is concentrated / not extended to other type of irrigation such as drip, atomization,etc
G.V.SatyanarayanaMazarruddin, SD (2013) [6]	Wireless Sensor Based Remote Monitoring System for Agriculture using ZigBee and GPS	In remote sensing	Remote monitoring is done/ but not extended to support system

2.2 IoT in Agriculture

IoT is a technology which connects stand alone equipments and autonomous devices to each other and users via Internet.

Table 2: IoT in Smart Farming

Author Name& Year	Title	Work done
Partha Pratim Ray (2017)[7]	Internet of things for smart agriculture: Technologies, practices and future direction	IoT applications and the specific issues and challenges related with IoT and different case studies were given
Abouzahir <i>et al.</i> (2017)[8]	IoT- Empowered Smart Agriculture: A Real-Time Light-Weight Embedded Segmentation System	Computed the performance and executed the smart agriculture in their work
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2014).[9]	The Application of Internet of Things in Agricultural means of production supply chain management	analyzes the application of IoT in product supply chain business processes
Minbo <i>et al.</i> (2013).[10]	Information Service System of Agriculture IoT	proposed an information system of agriculture Internet of Things based on distributed architecture

3. Proposed System Design

The Proposed system is designed using Arduino Uno open source Microcontroller board based on the Microchip ATmega328P microcontroller with a CPU Microchip AVR (8-bit),Memory SRAM, and Flash, EEPROM memory for storage purpose It uses the following components

3.1. Soil moisture sensor

This device can find out the soil moisture in volumetric units when it is interfaced with an Arduino System.

3.2 Temperature sensor

LM 35 is a precision temperature sensing device. It senses the variation in the temperature in the surrounding environment.

3.3.RTC – (Real Time Clock)

The DS1307 Real-Time Clock (RTC) is used to keep track of time and manage the calendar. In this system, the RTC starts when a seed is planted, and the planting date is recorded in the Arduino's EEPROM. This stored data is essential for determining the timely application of nutrients (fertilizers) and pesticides to the plant.

3.4. GSM

In this system, a GSM module based on the SIM800A, supporting dual frequencies of 900/1800 MHz, is utilized. GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) technology enables the transmission of alert messages to the user, notifying them when it's time to apply fertilizers and pesticides.

Fig1:Circuit Diagram

3.5. Relay and Solenoid Valve: The solenoid valve, controlled by a relay, automatically switches ON/OFF to regulate the application of nutrients to the field. This system works in conjunction with drip irrigation, ensuring the precise delivery of nutrients to the plants.

3.6. Wi-Fi

The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module is a standalone system-on-chip (SoC) featuring an integrated TCP/IP protocol stack, allowing any microcontroller to connect to a Wi-Fi network. It can either host an application directly or offload all Wi-Fi networking tasks from a separate application processor.

3.7. NPK Sensor

The soil NPK detects the content of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the soil.

3.8. LCD Display

The current temperature, humidity and soil moisture are shown in LCD Display.

Fig.2 The overall Architecture

3.9. Drip Irrigation and supply of nutrient to the soil

When the temperature readings exceed the threshold or the soil moisture level falls below the predefined value, the system activates or deactivates the solenoid valve to control the drip irrigation based on the conditions detected by the sensors. The temperature and soil moisture data are transmitted to the IoT server for further analysis and

decision-making. The system stores the seed planting date in memory and triggers an SMS via the GSM module on the scheduled fertilizer supply date. At this time, the system retrieves the Nitrogen, Phosphorous, and Potassium (NPK) values from the NPK sensor. Using fuzzy logic techniques, it supplies the optimal quantities of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium to the farm. The baseline nutrient levels in the soil are referenced from the TNAU Agritech database, as shown in the table below

Table 3: Nutrient Value

Nutrient	Low	Medium	High
Available Nitrogen(N)	<240Kg/ha	240-480 Kg/ha	>480 Kg/ha
Available Phosphorus(P)	<11.0Kg/ha	11-22 Kg/ha	> 22 Kg/ha
Available Potassium(K)	<110 Kg/ha	110-280 Kg/ha	>280 Kg/ha

The general soil nutrient value varies from plant to plant and the supply of the nutrient for the particular month for the corresponding plant will also vary. By giving the correct schedule of nutrient quantity, the smart farming system will take decisions accurately with the help of fuzzy logic technique and supply the required quantity to the farm. Solenoid valve is automatically switched off when the nutrient is supplied over the farm

Fig. 3 Fuzzy Based Automatic Nutrigation Conditions

4. Results and Discussions

Soil Moisture Sensor and humidity sensor sense the moisture contents of the field and send the details to the Server.

Fig.4. Sensor data of Temperature and Soil moisture

Comparison of Farming using Fuzzy Logic and Sensor with conventional Method of Farming

Table 4 Conventional Farming Vs Smart Farming

Resources	Needed	In Soil	To be Supplied	Conventional (Approximately)	% Waste	Sensor	% Waste
Water	>90 %	<30%		>60 %	>75(Approximately)	>60%	<10 (Approximately)
Nitrogen	480Kg/Hec	280.025 Kg/Hec	200 Kg/Hec	300 Kg/Hec	50	210 Kg/Hec	5
Phosphorous	21Kg/Hec	11 Kg/Hec	10Kg/Hec	16 Kg/Hec	60	12 Kg/Hec	20
Pottassium	280 Kg/Hec	100 Kg/Hec	180 Kg/Hec	250Kg/Hec	38.8	200 Kg/Hec	11

The above table clearly shows the result that sensor based farming produces the optimum result.

5. Conclusion

The system collects soil moisture, temperature and NPK using sensors and supply the required water and nutrient through drip irrigation. The result of the proposed system were seen in both water savings and supply of nutrient and overall yield is increased. It also alerts the farmer to supply the nutrient on date. All the data will be sent to the server simultaneously for monitoring and analyzing purpose.

6. Scope of the Work

In future, in addition to NPK more micro and macro nutrients can be supplied . Android version can also be added . insecticide detection can also be added to this system.

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